

Quantifying radiative heat flux and firebrand attack from wildfires at the Wildland-Urban Interface using physics-based models

Version 2

Description

The wildland-urban interface (WUI) refers to the area where human development and wildland or vegetative fuels intermix or overlap. The general trends in WUI dynamics indicate that the expansion of human settlements into previously uninhabited or sparsely populated areas will continue. This trend is primarily driven by population growth and urban sprawl, land use changes through the conversion of agricultural and/or forest areas into urban ones, economic and infrastructure developments in rural areas, and climate change.

Performance-based design approach empowers engineers to use extensively science-based knowledge to assess and quantify the thermal attack of wildfires on the built-environment at the WUI. The use of Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD)(using Fire Dynamics Simulator-FDS) tools is crucial to modelling and understanding fire spread and the impact of wildfires in the built environment assessing in detail heat transfer mechanisms and ignition potential of structures using full physics models. Specific focus will be devoted to the study of firebrands, targeting their generation, transport, accumulation and how they may cause new ignitions in the built environment, and to the study of the radiative heat flux. Complex numerical models will be developed to reproduce the experimental behaviour observed in real fire field tests, enabling extensive parametric studies to investigate critical and realistic scenarios that allow the development and implementation of tailored preventive measures to enhance the resilience and safety of the built environment. Coupling CFD with the finite element method will be conducted to assess the behaviour of materials with increasing temperature.

The obtained results will be disseminated through journal and conference papers and in webinars continuing the work that is being conducted in the scope of the ongoing

research project INTERFACESEGURA (PCIF/AGT/0062/2018). A PhD candidate funded by FCT is working on this specific topic.

Funder

Fundação para a Ciência e a Tecnologia, I.P. | FCT

Grant

Quantifying radiative heat flux and firebrand attack from wildfires at the Wildland-Urban Interface using physics-based models
(fct_____::2023.10892.CPCA.A2)

Researchers

Cesare Fiorini (0000-0003-3364-6628), Helder Craveiro

Organizations

Universidade de Coimbra

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: [Quantifying radiative heat flux and firebrand attack from wildfires at the Wildland-Urban Interface using physics-based models](#)

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Researchers:

[Cesare Fiorini \(0000-0003-3364-6628\)](#)

[Helder Craveiro](#)

Organizations:

Universidade de Coimbra

Contact: Craveiro Helder (heldercraveiro.eng@uc.pt)

2. Funding

Funding organizations: Fundação para a Ciência e a Tecnologia, I.P. | FCT

Grants: Quantifying radiative heat flux and firebrand attack from wildfires at the Wildland-Urban Interface using physics-based models (fct_____:2023.10892.CPCA.A2)

Project: Cite Project

3. License

License: AFL-3.0

Access Rights: Public

4. Templates

Descriptions

FCT - Template in English

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DOI: - 09/02/2026

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Template: [FCT - Template in English](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 DATA INFORMATION

1.1 What existing data will be re-used?

1.1.1 Will you re-use existing data for this project?

Yes

1.1.2 Which existing data you will re-use and under which terms of use?

All numerical results obtained are and will still be used to finalise scientific publications

1.1.3 Describe the data type you will re-use

Mainly numeric, specifically spreadsheets, but also images and video exploring the visual output from the CFD simulations.

1.1.4 Describe the format of data you will re-use

*.xls

1.2 What data will be created or produced?

1.2.1 Will new data be created in this project?

Yes

1.2.2 Describe the data you expect your research will generate.

Numeric (databases and spreadsheets), image and video from visualization of CFD simulations.

1.2.3 Describe the data format you expect your research will generate.

.xls

1.3 What is the data volume?

1.3.1 How much data storage will your project require in total?

10 – 100 GB

2 DOCUMENTATION AND METADATA

2.1 Documentation

2.1.1 Indicate what documentation will accompany the data.

Support documentation detailing the scenarios used for CFD model validation and calibration and details used for the parametric studies.

2.2 Metadata

2.2.1 Is there metadata associated with the data?

Yes

2.2.2 Indicate which metadata will be provided to help others identify and discover the data.

I will provide comprehensive metadata to ensure the reproducibility of the CFD simulations. This includes: WHO: Identification of researchers (including ORCIDs for Hélder Craveiro and Cesare Fiorini). WHERE: Geographic coordinates and topographic domain of the Wildland-Urban Interface (WUI) modeled. WHAT: Technical specifications of the Fire Dynamics Simulator (FDS 6.7.8) setup, including mesh density (10 cm), boundary conditions, and solver parameters. HOW: Documentation of the simulation workflow, initial ignition conditions using firebrands, and data processing methods recorded in a README.txt file.

2.2.3 Please identify the metadata standard(s) that apply.

CIM (Common Information Model)

2.2.4 Please identify the controlled vocabularies that apply.

To ensure interoperability, terms from the Environment Ontology (ENVO) will be used to describe Wildland-Urban Interface settings and vegetation species. Furthermore, all physical quantities and simulation outputs will adhere to Standard SI units (e.g., kW/m², °C, kg/s).

2.2.5 Please select the appropriate language for metadata.

Eng.

3 STORAGE AND SECURITY OF DATA AND METADATA

3.1 How will data and metadata be stored and backed up during the research?

3.1.1 Describe where the data and metadata will be stored during the project.

Institution networked research storage

3.1.3 Is there a policy in place for data backups during the project?

Yes

Data stored in personal cloud storage services

3.1.4 Please describe the type of backup.

Cloud backup

3.1.5 Please describe the frequency of backup.

Monthly

3.2 Protection and security of sensitive data

3.2.1 How will data security and protection of sensitive data be taken care of during the research?

Default security measures of the institution networked research storage

3.2.2 Please specify.

Access to simulation data on the HPC is restricted to the research team (Helder Craveiro and Cesare Fiorini) through secure SSH protocols and institutional

credentials. The project does not involve sensitive personal data (GDPR) or national security information.

4 PERSONAL DATA, INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY RIGHTS AND OWNERSHIP

4.1 How will you handle issues regarding the processing of personal information and intellectual property rights and ownership?

4.1.1 Will you process and/or store personal data during your project?

No

4.1.3 How will ownership of the data and intellectual property rights to the data be managed?

Hélder Craveiro (0000-0001-8590-5885)

UNIVERSIDADE DE COIMBRA

The intellectual property rights and ownership of the data produced during this project reside with the Universidade de Coimbra. The Principal Investigator (PI), Hélder Craveiro, is the primary person responsible for data management and has the authority to control access. The datasets, largely generated by the PhD researcher Cesare Fiorini as part of his doctoral thesis, will be managed according to the Open Access policies of the FCT and the RNCA. While the university retains ownership, the data will be made publicly available via the Zenodo repository once the 1-year embargo period—intended to protect the PhD defense and primary scientific publications—has expired.

5 DATA SHARING AND LONG-TERM PRESERVATION

5.1 Long-term data preservation

5.1.1 How will data be selected for long-term preservation?

All data resulting from the project will be preserved for at least 10 years

5.2 Data available for re-use

5.2.1 What data will be made available for re-use?

All data resulting from the project will be made available

5.2.3 When will the data be available for re-use, and for how long will the data be available?

Data available as soon as article is published

A temporary embargo period will be applied to the dataset. The data will be fully accessible to the public immediately after the successful defense of the PhD thesis currently being developed by the researcher Cesare Fiorini, ensuring the priority of publication and intellectual property rights, since 2 journal papers are currently under preparation.

5.2.4 In which repository will the data be archived and made available for re-use, and under which license?

Couldn't find it? Insert it manually

ZENODO

5.2.5 Please confirm if:

The repository is aggregated in OpenAIRE

5.2.6 Please indicate whether a persistent identifier will be pursued.

Yes

DOI

5.2.7 Under which license will the data be archived and made available for re-use?

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

5.2.8 Describe your strategy for publishing the analysis software that will be generated in this project.

No new analysis software was developed in this project. However, users require specific open-source tools to access and interpret the data. Specifically, the Fire Dynamics Simulator (FDS version 6.7.8) and the Smokeview visualization tool are necessary to run the provided input files (.fds) and visualize the output results. Both tools are publicly available through the National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST).

6 RESPONSIBILITIES AND RESOURCES

6.1 Responsibilities and resources for data management

6.1.1 Who (for example role, position, and institution) will be responsible for data management?

Hélder Craveiro (0000-0001-8590-5885)

UNIVERSIDADE DE COIMBRA

After publication and defense of the PhD thesis and publication of the 2 journal papers under preparation the data will be made available by the responsible.

6.1.2 What resources (for example financial and time) will be dedicated to data management and ensuring that data will be FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable)?

Time will be devoted to data curation, metadata enrichment and documentation. The computational costs (210000 core-hours) were fully covered by the FCT Advanced Computing Grant.

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